

AI: from a long Winter to a blossoming Spring

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INTRODUCTION:

Despite being a relatively new research field Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been shaped by huge expectations and colossal failures. After several stagnation periods, or "long winters", AI is flourishing and impacting business at an unforeseen rate. Behind this success is a technology widely known as Deep Neural Networks or Deep Learning (DL). In this talk I will summarise the key elements of DL and why it is such a transformative force for almost every business. DL, however, come at a cost: it requires lot of data, it's complex to train the models, and often they are black boxes. I will include some use cases and recommendations where to use and not to use is in an organization.

AIM:

This presentation is intentioned for a mix audience, from academics to data scientists, data engineers, entrepreneurs and business developers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

RESULTS:

We present some examples of applications from recommendation algorithms to image processing. In particular, we analyze convolutional LSTMs for video processing. We show that temporal information is important to segment ultra-sound images and improve detection of arteries and veins.

CONCLUSIONS:

This presentation will present some key findings and implications in business of Deep Learning, especially for medical video processing.

KEYWORDS:

Convolutional LSTM, Video segmentation, image processing, Deep Learning

BIOGRAPHY:

Armando Vieira is a Physicist turned into a data scientist. He started working on machine learning after his PhD in Physics in 1997. From the beginning he was an aficionado of Artificial Neural Networks, and recently he is focused on Deep Neural Networks, especially for unsupervised and semi-supervised learning problems. He has more than 50 publications and worked as a Data Scientist consultant on several companies and Start-ups.

